

ADVOCACY FOR JUSTICIABILITY OF RIGHT TO HEALTH IN NIGERIA

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ABSTRACT: Under the Nigerian the Nigerian Constitution, some rights are justiciable while others are non-justiciable. Non-justiciable rights cannot be enforced in Courts notwithstanding their recognition in international human right treaties or instruments. Against this backdrop, the paper analysed relevant constitutional provisions and decided cases on health rights in order to ascertain its status under the Nigerian Constitution. The paper found that right to health is a non-justiciable, hence, its denial or violation cannot be judicially redressed. The paper also established that, notwithstanding ratified international treaties that affirm Nigeria's commitment to recognising and upholding the right to health, because of the supremacy of the Constitution, it cannot be enforced in Courts as international treaties do not trump Nigeria's Constitution. It was recommended among other things that Nigeria's Constitution should be amended to guarantee health as a justiciable right without which other rights, especially those that relate to life and well being, will remain illusory.

Keywords: *health, food, justiciable, life, right*

1.0 Introduction

As a preliminary point, it needs to be emphasised that the right to health is universal, meaning everyone is entitled to

it. Right to health is guaranteed in many international human rights instruments and treaties beginning with the cornerstone of human rights, the Universal Declaration of Human Rights (UDHR), 1948. Under *article 25* of the UDHR, 1948, it is provided that “everyone has a right to a standard of living adequate for the health and well-being of himself and his family including food, clothing, housing and medical care and necessary social services and the right to security in the event of unemployment, sickness, disability, widowhood, old age or other lack of livelihood in circumstances beyond his control”. The right to good health and well-being also finds copious expressions in *article 12* of the International Covenant on Economic, Social and Cultural Rights (ICESCR), 1966; *articles 10(h), 11(f), 12 and 14(b)* of the Convention on the Elimination of all Forms of Discrimination against Women (CEDAW), 1979; *article 24(2)(d)* of the Convention of the Rights of the Child (CRC), 1989; *article 5(e)(iv)* of the Convention on the Elimination of All Forms of Racial Discrimination (CERD), 1969 and *article 16* of African Union midwifed Africa Charter on Human and Peoples Rights, 1981. Good health and wellbeing are derivatives of right to life guaranteed in *article 3* of the UDHR, 1948; *article 6* of the ICCPR; 1966 and *article 4* of the ACHPR, 1981. Furthermore, Goal 3 of the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals is to ensure healthy lives and promote well-being for all ages while Goal 3 of the African Union Agenda 2063 is on Healthy and Well-Nourished Citizens. This specific goal directly incorporates the right to health by aiming for adequate investment in quality healthcare access and improved health outcomes.

Against the foregoing backdrop, notwithstanding the above flowery provisions, this research effort examines the extent to which the right to health is guaranteed under the Nigerian Constitution. This has become necessary because of the classification of the right to health as one that cannot be inquired into by the Court and the necessity to fashion out what must be done to attain that desirable standard in Nigeria. For ease of understanding, the paper is divided into the following remaining segments namely- Overarching nature of right to health; Supremacy of the national Constitution; Status of right to health in Nigeria; Case for making the right to health justiciable; and Conclusion.

2.0 Overarching nature of right to health

According to the World Health Organisation, “health is a state of complete physical, mental and social well-being and not merely the absence of disease or infirmity. The enjoyment of the highest attainable standard of health is one of the fundamental rights of every human being without distinction of race, religion and political belief, economic or social condition”. Health is comprehensive because health is wealth and when health is lost, something is lost. The World Health Organisation further maintains that “health is much more than the absence of disease or infirmity as it is a state of complete physical, mental and social well-being.” On its part, the National Human Rights Commission of Nigeria defined right to health as “the right of everyone to the enjoyment of the highest attainable standard of physical and mental health. Right to health extends to ensuring clean water, sanitation, food, nutrition and through a comprehensive system of healthcare”. Adequate food is also required to maintain excellent physical and mental health conditions. Besides, education and learning cannot be sustained in an environment pervading with hunger and starvation. It has also been clarified that “the right to health is not the same as the right to be healthy. There is a widespread misperception that our health must be guaranteed by the State.” Good health is influenced by several factors, including an individual’s socio-economic status and biological composition, genetics etcetera, which are not directly within the authority of States. Importantly, the right to health refers to the freedom to enjoy a range of products, services, facilities, and environments that are required for its implementation. Because of this, the term “right to the highest attainable standard of physical and mental health” is a more appropriate description of it than “an unconditional right to be healthy”.

According to the United Nations, the right to health is an inclusive right, covering a wide range of elements that help us to lead healthy lives - things like safe drinking water, adequate sanitation, safe food, healthy working conditions and more. Other key aspects of the right to health are: (i) Accessibility: Health facilities, goods and services must be affordable, within reach physically and on the basis of non-discrimination. (ii) Availability: Functioning public health and health-care facilities, goods and services must be in sufficient quantity. (iii) Acceptability: The facilities,

goods and services should respect medical ethics, and be gender-sensitive and culturally-appropriate. (iv) Good quality: Health facilities, goods and services must be scientifically- and medically-appropriate, and in good working condition. (v) Participation: Health care beneficiaries should have a voice in designing and implementing health policies which affect them. (vi) Accountability: Providers and States should be held accountable for meeting human rights obligations for public health. People should have the possibility of seeking effective remedies for violations such as the denial of health services. (vii) Freedoms: People must be free from non-consensual medical treatments, such as medical experiments or forced sterilization; torture; and other cruel, inhuman or degrading treatment or punishment. (viii) Entitlements: People are entitled to the opportunity to enjoy the highest attainable level of health; the right to prevention, treatment and control of diseases; access to essential medicines; and maternal, child and reproductive health, among other entitlements.

From the foregoing therefore, in this paper, the right to health connotes the legally guaranteed opportunity legally availed to everyone to enjoyment of excellent mental and physical well being within the national rights system. It is the contention in this paper that where the right to healthiness is not guaranteed and declared justiciable within the national or domestic rights system, it amounts to inchoate or no guarantee in practical terms. On the strength of this thesis therefore, the next segment will be devoted to discussion of the supremacy of the national Constitution as justification for advocacy in this paper that the right to health should be constitutionally protected and declared enforceable in the Courts.

3.0 Supremacy of the national Constitution

The extant Constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria (CFRN), 1999 as amended is the supreme law, *the fons et origo and the grundnorm*. This principle owes its origin to the provisions of *section 1(1) and (3)* of the Constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria, 1999 as amended. *Section 1(1)* enacts as follows: “This Constitution is Supreme and its provisions shall have binding force on the authorities and persons throughout the Federal Republic of Nigeria” while *sub-section (3)* thereof enacts that “If any other law is inconsistent with the provisions of this

Constitution, this Constitution shall prevail, and that other law shall, to the extent of the inconsistency, be void.” It was held recently in *CBN v Ochife & Ors*, that the Constitution is the grundnorm, the basic law of the land. It stands head and shoulders above any other law or instrument enacted by the National Assembly, State House of Assembly or any other person or authority empowered in that regard. It is from the Constitution that every other enactment or instrument derives their validity and binding force. Pre-eminence of the Constitution is recognised in a long line of decided cases such as *NPF & Ors v Police Service Commission & Anor*, *Shelim & Anor v Goban*, *Sifax (Nig) Ltd v Phoenix Capital Ltd & Anor*, and *Olugbemi v State*.

As an extension of the pre-eminence of the Nigerian Constitution, it is good law that treaties are also subordinated to the Nigerian Constitution. Though treaties are Statutes of international flavour that are applicable by Nigerian Courts when incorporated into the body of municipal laws, but they not trump constitutional provisions. It bears repeating that in *Abacha v Fawehinmi*, the Supreme Court held that the general rule is that a treaty which has been incorporated into the body of the municipal laws ranks at par with the municipal laws. It is not promoted to higher status relative “to other municipal legislations”. The Courts must uphold the African Charter as it is now part of the laws of Nigeria like all other laws. Although it is clothed with international flavour, if there is a clash between it and another legislation, its provisions will predominate over that other legislation for the reason that it is presumed that the legislature does not intend to breach an international obligation. However, the African Charter is inferior to the Constitution and its international character cannot preclude the National Assembly from invalidating it.

Based on the doctrine of hegemony of the national Constitution, the judiciary is consecrated with power to declare unconstitutional any legislative or executive actions, decisions or directives that are done or carried on in flagrant violation, disobedience or disregard of the Constitution. It was held In *PRP & Ors v KESIEC & Anor* that

“The Constitution of a nation, in this instance the 1999 Constitution of Nigeria is binding on every person and institution in Nigeria and any action taking contrary to the Constitution will be declared null and void.

See *PDP v Sylva* (2012) 13 NWLR (Pt 1316) 85, *Udenwa v Uzodinma* (2013) 5 NWLR (Pt. 1346) 94. The Supreme Court made this very clear in the case of *NPF & Ors v Police Service Commission & Anor* (2023) LPELR- 60782 (SC): ‘It is equally imperative to restate the elementary principle of the dominance of the Constitution. The Constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria is the grundnorm, the basic law of the land. It stands head and shoulders above any other law or instrument enacted by the National Assembly, State House of Assembly or any other person or authority empowered in that regard. It is from the Constitution that every other enactment or instrument derive their validity and binding force. The dogma of the ascendancy of the Nigerian Constitution is traceable to *section 1(1) and (3)* of the Constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria, 1999 (as altered) ... per Jauro, JSC.’

The Constitution is therefore the benchmark or touchstone upon which the constitutionality of any executive, legislative or judicial act is considered.

4.0 Status of right to health in Nigeria

Discussion in this segment of the paper may be prefaced with the question whether any constitutional guarantee of health in Nigeria exists? As a direct answer, what may be termed the right to health in Nigeria is expressed as one of the “Social Objectives” contained in *section 17* of the CFRN, 1999 as amended. Specifically, *section 17 (3) (c) and (d)* enact that “the State shall direct its policy towards ensuring that- (c) the health, safety and welfare of all persons in employment are safeguarded and not endangered or abused; (d) there are adequate medical and health facilities for all persons” From the foregoing, it could be seen that the provision in *section 17 (3) (c)* relates to “health of persons in employment” only while the provision of *section 17 (3) (d)* relates “to all persons”. Going by the pattern of protection of rights under the Nigerian Constitution, it is safe to argue that there no guarantee of the right to health as fundamental right that is justiciable. The “social objectives” form part of the “Fundamental Objectives and Directive Principles of State Policy” contained in Chapter II of the CFRN, 1999 as amended that are not justiciable. Under *section 6(6)(c)* of the CFRN, 1999 as amended it is enacted that “the judicial powers shall

not, except as otherwise provided by the Constitution, extend to any issue or question as to whether any act or omission by any authority or person or as to whether any law or any judicial decision is in conformity with the Fundamental Objectives and Directive Principles of State Policy set out in Chapter II of the Constitution.” It is important to explain further that it is not every civil, political, economic, social and cultural right that is constitutionally protected and rendered enforceable in the Courts. In the recent 2025 decision in *Okonjo-Iweala v Fawehinmi & Ors*, the apex Court reiterated that a justiciable matter is the type of case or dispute which will justify the exercise of the Court of its judicial power. Therefore, no Nigerian Court will waste its precious time entertaining a matter that is not justiciable and moreso, where expressly declared non-justiciable under the Constitution.

Specifically, Chapter IV of the CFRN, 1999 as amended guarantees the justiciability of the following twelve fundamental rights namely: (1) Right to life in *section 33*; (2) Right to dignity of human person in *section 34*; (3) Right to personal liberty in *section 35*; (4) Right to fair hearing in *section 36*; (5) Right to private and family life in *section 37*; (6) Right to freedom of thought, conscience and religion in *section 38*; (7) Right to freedom of expression and the press in *section 39*; (8) Right to peaceful assembly and association in *section 40*; (9) Right to freedom of movement in *section 41*; (10) Right to freedom from discrimination in *section 42*; (11) Right to acquire and own immovable property anywhere in Nigeria in *section 43*; and (12) Right to prompt payment of compensation upon compulsory acquisition of property in *section 44*. These twelve fundamental rights protected under Chapter IV of the Constitution are full-blown rights that are justiciable and the courts accord them robust judicial recognition. Unlawful derogations, violations or infractions of any of these rights are enforceable under the Fundamental Rights (Enforcement Procedure) Rules, 2009 made pursuant to *section 46 (3)* of the CFRN, 1999 as amended.

Conversely, economic, social and cultural rights classified as “fundamental objectives and directive principles of State policy” in Chapter II of the CFRN, 1999 as amended are non-justiciable by virtue of the provisions of *section 6 (6) (c)* of the same Constitution thereby making them mirages or illusory rights. These are-political objectives in *section 15*, economic objectives in *section 16*; social objectives

in *section 17*; educational objectives in *section 18*; foreign policy objectives in *section 19*; environmental objectives in *section 20*; directive on Nigeria cultures in *section 21*; obligation of the mass media in *section 22*; national ethics in *section 23*; and duties of the citizen in *section 24* of the CFRN, 1999 as amended. Conclusively, right to health cannot be enforced in Court in the event of its denial, violation or infringement. In *Uwazuruonye v Governor of Imo State & Ors*, it was established as hornbook law that justiciable matter is one in which the plaintiff has a cause of action. Nigerian Courts only consider justiciable issues or controversy and do not bother spending precious judicial time with hypothetical disputes or one that is academic or moot.

It may not be out of place to point out that aside the above constitutional provision on health, some other legal provisions relating to health in Nigeria include but are not limited to the following:

- a) The body of international treaties ratified that affirm Nigeria's obligation to health such as the ICESCR, 1966 (ratified on 29 July, 1993); CERD (ratified on 16 October, 1967); CEDAW (ratified 23 April, 1984); CRC, 1989; ICCPR, 1966, (ratified on 29 July, 1993); the Convention against Torture and Other Cruel, Inhuman or Degrading Treatment or Punishment, (ratified on 28 June, 2001; and ACHPR, 1981 (ratified in 1983).
- b) African Charter on Human and Peoples' Rights (Ratification and Enforcement) Act, 1983 which ratified the application in Nigeria of the ACHPR, 1981. *Section 16 (1)* of the ACHPR provides that "every individual shall have the right to enjoy the best attainable state of physical and mental health". This provision is bogged down by the issue of non-justiciability erected in *section 6 (6) (c)* of the CFRN, 1999 as amended. The provisions of the African Charter were held not to be superior to the provisions of the national Constitution in *Abacha v Fawehinmi*.
- c) There are also provisions appertaining to various aspects of health contained in sundry legislations like National Health Act, 2014; National Health Insurance Scheme Act, 2022 that repealed the National Health Insurance Scheme Act, 1999 and made "health insurance mandatory for all citizens and legal residents";

National Mental Health Act, 2021, which established the mental health services department “to promote and protect the rights of persons with intellectual, psychosocial or cognitive disabilities, provide for enhancement and regulation of mental health services in Nigeria; and for related matters”. *Section 15 (1)* of the National Mental Health Act, 2021 provides that “a person with a mental health condition has the right to appropriate, affordable and accessible- (a) physical and mental health care and services, (b) counselling, (c) rehabilitation, and (d) after-care support, to facilitate reintegration into the community”. Furthermore, under *section 13* of the Childs Right Act, 2003 it is provided extensively as follows:

‘(1) Every child is entitled to enjoy the best attainable state of physical, mental and spiritual health. (2) Every Government, parent, guardian, institution, service, agency, organisation, or body responsible for the care of a child shall endeavour to provide for the child the best attainable health. (3) Every Government in Nigeria shall- (a) endeavour to reduce infant and child mortality rate; (b) ensure the provision of necessary medical assistance and health care services to all children with emphasis on the development of primary health care; (c) ensure the provision of adequate nutrition and safe drinking water; (d) ensure the provision of good hygiene and environment sanitation; (e) combat disease and malnutrition within the framework of primary health care through the application of appropriate technology; (f) ensure appropriate health care for expectant and nursing mother; and (g) support, through technical and financial means, the mobilisation of national and local community resources in the development of primary health care for children. (4) Every parent, guardian or person having the care and custody of a child under the age of two years shall ensure that the child is provided with full immunisation.’

Lastly, in *section 1* of the Compulsory Treatment and Care of Victims of Gunshot Act, 2017, it is provided that “every hospital in Nigeria whether public or private shall accept or receive, for immediate and adequate treatment with or without police clearance, any person with a gunshot wound”. The snag here is that none of these

legislations can pass for or substitute constitutional guarantee of right to health. It is the contention in this paper that piecemeal recognition of health-related rights is counterproductive.

5.0 Case for making the right to health justiciable

As already noted, the constitutional dichotomy between justiciable Chapter IV (fundamental rights) provisions and non-justiciable Chapter II (fundamental objectives and directive principles of state policy) makes it impossible for violation of the right to health to be enforced in the Courts. It remains to add that in *Ufomba v INEC*, it was held that “justiciable” means “A case or dispute properly brought before a Court of justice: capable of being disposed of judicially.” Thus, following this principle, breach or denial of the right to health cannot be disposed of judicially. The relevant concern therefore is whether this state of things should be allowed to remain unaddressed given the importance of health and its close link to right to life and well-being. The direct answer to this poser is in the negative.

The non-justiciability of the right to health remains the greatest hindrance to enjoyment of good health and well-being in Nigeria. Human rights are holistic, indivisible, indivisible and mutually reinforcing. No one human rights is greater, better or more important than the other. There can be no enjoyment of civil and political rights without economic, social and cultural rights. It is indubitable that the right to life declared justiciable under *section 33* of the CFRN, 1999 as amended is not meaningful without the right to health being guaranteed. In Nigeria, the right to health is given very scant consideration or attention to the extent that ill-health seldom forms a plausible ground for bail. Ill-health is only accepted as exceptional circumstance for bail as held in *Jammal v State*. However, in *George & Ors v FRN*, it was held that it will be negated where applicants have unrestricted opportunity to health care or where the health condition of the applicant is not shown to be life threatening. Every case must be treated according to its peculiar set of facts and circumstances. In *Nwogu v FRN*, The Appellant predicated his application for bail on grounds of ill health. The Federal High Court refused it. On appeal, it was held that illness of a person in custody does not automatically entitle him to be admitted on bail unless there are compelling reasons so to do. While in detention or custody, it is

the responsibility of the authorities in the facility where he is being held to afford him access to proper medical care. It will however be compelling reason to admit the detainee to bail where the nature of the ailment is such that poses a real health hazard to others and there are no facilities available for either quarantine or treatment of that kind of illness. The materials furnished by the Appellant at the lower Court did not disclose any ill health that posed a real health hazard to others in custody. The refusal of bail was therefore held not to be not injudicious rather a proper exercise of judicial discretion.

On a comparative note, when put side by side with the Bill of Rights contained in the South Africa Constitution, 1996, it will be clearly seen that there is no direct and reasonable constitutional guarantee of health-related rights in Nigeria. The right to health care, food water and social security is expressly guaranteed in *section 27* of the Constitution of the Republic of South Africa, 1996 to the effect that- “(1) Everyone has the right to have access to health care services, including reproductive health care; sufficient food and water; and social security, including, if they are unable to support themselves and their dependents, appropriate social assistance. (2) No one may be refused emergency medical treatment under *section 27 (3)*.” Under *section 27 (2)* of the same Constitution, it is enacted that “the state must take reasonable legislative and other measures, within its available resources, to achieve the progressive realisation of each of these rights”. This is unlike what is obtainable under *section 17 (3) (d)* of the Constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria, 1999 as amended where the right to health is a non-justiciable social objective. The Constitutional Court of South Africa gave clear recognition to economic, social and cultural rights in the case of *Van Biljon v Minister of Correctional Services*. In this case, the applicants were HIV-infected prisoners who sought, inter alia, a declaratory order that their right to adequate medical treatment entitled them to the provision of expensive anti-retroviral medication. It was contended on behalf of the applicants that because the right to adequate medical treatment was guaranteed in the Bill of Rights, prison authorities could not on the basis of lack of funds, refuse to provide treatment which was medically indicated. This argument was accepted by the court. The apex Court reasoned that lack of funds could not be an answer to a prisoner’s constitutional claim to adequate treatment as a prisoner had a constitutional right to

that form of medical treatment which was “adequate”. The applicants’ prayer was granted and the respondents were ordered to supply them with the combination of anti-retroviral medication which had been prescribed for them for as long as such medication continued to be prescribed. In addition, in the South African cases of *B & Ors v the Minister for Correctional Services and Others* and *Soobramoney v Minister of Health, KwaZulu-Natal*, the right to health and good healthcare under *sections 27 (3) and 35 (2) (e)* respectively of the Constitution of the Republic of South Africa, 1996 were upheld. On the contrary, in the Nigerian case of *Oronto Douglas v Shell Petroleum Co. Ltd* the plaintiff went to court to enforce the right to a safe and liveable environment guaranteed by *article 24* of the ACHPR. He contended that contrary to the environmental impact assessment law, the defendants engaged in the construction of a hazardous liquefied natural gas plant without the requisite environmental impact assessment study. The High Court refused to entertain the suit on grounds of *locus standi* while at the Appeal Court stage, the case was remitted back to the High Court for hearing.

In sum, these judicial decisions and comparative excursion to South Africa clearly justify the need to accord the right to health the status of justiciability under the Nigerian Constitution. It is therefore strongly advocated that there should be repeal of the provisions of *section 6 (6) (c)* of the CFRN, 1999 as amended and wholesale provision for constitutional guarantee and justiciability of the right to health as a fundamental and justiciable right. Nigeria will do well to emulate the constitutional protection of right to health as applicable under the Bill of Rights South Africa.

6.0 Conclusion

It is unarguable that the right to health is universal given its importance and its close affinity to life. Based on critique of the lopsided constitutional provisions, this paper has made strong advocacy for making the right to health a fundamental and justiciable right in Nigeria. Continued retention of right to health as a non-justiciable “Social Objective” under the Nigerian Constitution is both unhelpful and counterproductive. It is submitted that unless and until right to health which promotes good health and well-being is made justiciable (the denial, breach or violation of which can be enforced in the Courts), the constitutional guarantee of

other rights especially that of life under the Nigerian Constitution will remain meaningless.

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